

Interpreters in The Time of Crisis: Borders and Barriers

المترجمون الفوريون في ظل الأزمات: الحواجز والحدود

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Abstract

The work of interpreters in frontlines is completely different from that of community interpreters. It needs advanced skills and competencies, in addition to resilience and a amenability to survive and prepare to face multiple risks. The language and culture barriers are the most pressing challenges facing conflict interpreters. Besides, diversity of culture, society norms, and hostile nature have a huge impact on the interpreters' work. The greatest obstacle to international understanding is the barrier of language (Kirkpatrick, 2020). 10 Yemeni interpreters working in conflict zones in Yemen were selected using an open-ended questionnaire to explore if they face challenges and barriers in their work as interpreters. For this purpose, the paper aimed to identify

the barriers and challenges that encounter interpreters in conflict zones in Yemen. The findings showed that interpreters encounter many challenges, including linguistic, social, cultural, and psychological challenges, in addition to pressure work, translation lost, workload, security threatening, diversity of dialects, diversity of society, workload, and term conflicts. The findings also showed that most interpreters are affected by cultural and psychological factors more than linguistical and social ones. The study recommended the interpreters to be aware of cultural sensitivity and to avoid psychological pressure and tension .

Key words: conflict, cultural diversity, pressure, language barrier, conflict zone interpreters, society, social.

المترجمون الفوريون في ظل الأزمات: الحواجز والحدود

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(1) باحث دكتوراه في دراسات الترجمة

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جامعة صنعاء

ملخص

العاملين في مناطق الصراع. تظهر النتائج أن المترجمين الفوريين يواجهون العديد من التحديات، بما في ذلك التحديات اللغوية والاجتماعية والثقافية والنفسية، بالإضافة إلى عوامل أخرى خارجية وداخلية، على سبيل المثال ضغوط العمل، والترجمة المفقودة، وعبء العمل، والتهديد الأمني، وتنوع اللهجات، وتنوع المجتمع، والتخويف، وتضارب المصطلحات. وتظهر نتائج البيانات أيضاً أن معظم المترجمين الفوريين يتأثرون بالعوامل الثقافية والنفسية أكثر من العوامل اللغوية والاجتماعية. وأوصت الدراسة المترجمين بأن يكونوا على دراية بالحساسية الثقافية وتجنب الضغط النفسي والتوتر. هناك حاجة للمزيد من الدراسات في هذا المجال.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الصراع، التنوع الثقافي، الضغوط، حواجز اللغة، المترجمون الفوريون، المجتمع، الجوانب الاجتماعية والجوانب النفسية.

إن عمل المترجمين الفوريين في نقاط التماس يختلف تماماً عن عمل المترجمين الفوريين في المجتمع. إن ذلك العمل يتطلب مهارات خاصة وكفاءات متقدمة بالإضافة إلى المرونة والرغبة القوية في البقاء ومواجهة المخاطر المحتملة المتعددة. تعد حواجز اللغة والثقافة من أكثر العقبات التي تواجه المترجمين الفوريين العاملين في مناطق الحروب. إلى جانب تنوع الثقافة، فإن أعراف المجتمع والطبيعة المعادية لها تأثير كبير على عمل المترجمين الفوريين. أكبر عقبة أمام التفاهم الدولي هي حاجز اللغة (كيريكاتريك، 2020). في هذه الورقة العلمية، تم اختيار عينة من (10) مترجمين فوريين محترفين يعملون في مناطق الصراع في اليمن، وتم استخدام استبانة مفتوحة لاستكشاف ما إذا كان المترجمون الفوريون يواجهون تحديات وعوائق في عملهم كمترجمين فوريين في مناطق الصراع في اليمن. وتهدف هذه الورقة إلى تحديد التحديات التي تواجه المترجمين الفوريين

1. Introduction:

“Translators and interpreters’ role in conflict zones has attracted a huge interest in recent years, as the need for language experts and professional interpreters are increased” (Askew & Salama-Carr, 2011). Simultaneous interpretation is an active component of dialogue, negotiation, conversation, meetings, mediations, conferences, seminars, health groups, delegations, deliberations, and consultations. Amidst many interpretation tasks, interpretation in conflict zones is unique, due to the nature of the setting, the context and the environment that surrounds it. Therefore, the task of interpreters is seen as more challenging. It has no control over the flow of the source speaker’s diction. Interpreters should be more focused on the rhythm, speed of speaking, tone and accent of each speaker. Various interference during interpretation tasks significantly affect the performance of the interpreter. Among them are cultural, social, linguistic, psychological and geographical factors. Thus, the interpreter finds himself/herself in multi-tasking work. Interpretation in conflict areas is essential and complicated (Ruiz Rosendo & Persaud, 2016). It is difficult to understand the interpreter’s mission in conflict zones without studying the obstacles and challenges he/she must face in the workplace.

The nature of each country may be different. But the challenges of interpretation remain the same. Since the turn of the last century, the world has experienced an abnormal increase in conflicts and wars, unlike ever before. It required the existence of a linguistic medium for transferring and making information substantial during mediation, conflicts, or intermediate wars. Interpreting in conflict zones are not an easy task. However, up to a point that the relations between the parties involved in conflict tend to be complicated. Interpreters may potentially play an important role in intelligence work performed before and during a given conflict (Moser-Mercer & Bali, 2008). Noting that nowadays conflict attracts the media and scholarly community, this is not a new phenomenon, but it is rooted from long times, interpreting in conflict zones is fairly a new topic. In the current status, conflict, war, dispute is a part of our lives, and has been since the beginning of immemorial times. The role of interpreters and translators in relation to violent conflicts is a complex, dynamic and multi-faceted one, whether they participate directly in war zones or more indirectly in legal or humanitarian contexts or in relation to written texts (Inghilleri & Harding, 2010, p. 165). According to Inghilleri (2005), “Given the present constitution of the interpreting profession as a ‘zone of uncertainty’, the status of interpreters’ knowledge remains vulnerable to exercises of power outside of their control” (p. 81).

Therefore, this paper will address the challenges and obstacles faced by interpreters in conflict zones based on the interpreters' perspectives and baseline studies. Moser-Mercer et al., (2014), classified challenges faced by field interpreters essentially fall into three categories: language- and culture-related challenges, role-related challenges, and emotional challenges (p. 141). Many challenges and obstacles lie ahead. Under the fluid aspects of profound meanings and concepts and based on humble researcher experience and knowledge. The challenges will be categorized in four dimensions (cultural, linguistic, social, psychological).

Conflict Zones: its” 1. a struggle for power, property, etc. and “2. strong disagreement between people, groups, etc., that results in often angry argument” and “3.a difference that prevents agreement: disagreement between ideas, feelings, etc. (Merriam-Webster, n.d.)

In the current study defined as the areas that two parts made disagreement, armed conflict and fighting

War Zones: “a zone in which belligerents are waging war broadly: an area marked by extreme violence” (Merriam-Webster, n.d.)

In the current study defined as the areas that witnessed war and gunfire it's also a duplicate name of conflict zones.

Schizoid Character: “: having mutually contradictory or antagonistic parts: changing frequently between opposite states” Merriam-Webster. (n.d.).

In the current study defined as description to multiple risky tasks that interpreters may act in conflict zones.

2. Statement of Problem

The last ten years have witnessed a significant escalation in the waves of armed conflict, especially in the Middle East, which has become a focus of conflict and armed movements, which has exacerbated the humanitarian situation. That required an urgent human aid intervention from the international community, upon that the presence of interpreters and language mediators emerged as a point of contact between foreign organizations and the locals. Recently translation and crisis wave began with several researchers and translation specialists that call for establishing the Translation and Crisis Center, which focused mainly about translation and crises, which became the product of the hour such as Mona Baker, Anthony Beam, Khaled Al Shehari, Rachel Nolan, Frederick and others. Therefore, the researcher interested

to delve into this field due to the lack of research in the field of translation and crises, especially in the Yemeni context.

In the current paper the researcher tackles barriers that encounter interpreters who are working in conflict zones in Yemen.

3. Objective of the study

This paper aims to identify the barriers and challenges that encounter interpreters who are working in conflict zones in Yemen.

4. Question of the study

What are the barriers and challenges that encounter interpreters who are working in conflict zones in Yemen?

5. Significance of the study

This study will open new horizons in interpreting studies approaches in conflict zones, it opens the door before novice, practitioners, professional language holders who are willing to involving in interpreting fields. It paves the way before researchers and scholars for further depth studies in interpreting in conflict zones.

6. Literature Review

Though limited number of literatures that wrote about translation and conflict in Yemen, however, discussing the Yemeni situation is part of a global situation, so number of researchers probed in this field, Moreno-Bello, (2021) indicated that the role of interpreters as language assistance, the armed and local interpreters are involved to facilitate the meeting between the Spanish army and the Lebanese civilian population. The work of the interpreter involves multiple and various tasks that include all operations on the ground, such as support, backup, coordination, communication, liaising, mediation, facilitation, clarification and serving. Therefore, it is not surprising that the interpreter is exposed to many psychological, and social pressures and faces many cultural and linguistic factors. Since 2014, Yemen has been in the grip of a humanitarian crisis, Yemen has been going through a historical turning juncture that affected the geography of the land and the future of the country. Therefore, the interventions of the international community come in response to the call of the United Nations to meet the humanitarian and relief needs including medicine, food, and shelter.

According to Moreno Bello, (2014) Interpreting in conflict areas has played a critical role in the record of wars. in diplomatic and peacekeeping missions in war areas, the interpreters are the only focal point military observers have with the culture

and peoples there. With the exacerbation of the Yemeni crisis, the need for language assistants and interpreters increased to provide assistance and facilitate the work of relief organizations and as a focal and liaising point between the warring parties. Given its roles, interpreters in zones of conflict are conducting the same job, for example, the local interpreter in Iraq face very dangerous situations: they are likely to put their lives on the line of loss or death. They accused them of assisting American troops and of treating them as traitors and collaborators of American forces (Takeda, 2009). Therefore, depending on the type and nature of the interpreter's work, interpreters face in-society's eyes that full of accusations, detractors, and allegations of treason. Therefore, the work of an interpreter in conflict areas is not an easy task, as it permanently puts his life at risk and is exposed to death or physically eliminating, especially in countries where there are many ethnicities and nationalities. Todorova, (2016), the key role of interpreters is to facilitate communication, conflict mediation situations. and third-party intervention very often surpass the usual role and skills needed by interpreters in any other situations. The intervention of a third party often exceeds the usual role of the interpreters in any situation.

6.1. The ideology of interpreting in conflict zones

Ideology and interpretation in conflict zones depend on the interpretation of languages as actual warfare so on. The dichotomy between interpreting and translating is an important point. The interpreters and language assistant could act per required situation, sometimes considered as an idealized perspective of the interpreter's work as a mediator or as a schizoid character in conflictual situations. This character could play and act some unexpected in such situation so schizoid personality of interpreter comes naturally as natural react against external phenomena (D'Amore et al., 2016). Yemen is faced the largest humanitarian crisis cross the world, according to Al-Shehari, (2019) interpreting in crisis trends to be based on ad hoc solutions. The interpreters and language holders are working with international organization to support human and relief operations.

6.2. Interpreters in the heart of the conflict – Challenges and Difficulties

Interpreters in the field of translation faced such challenges and difficulties base on their work situation, including cultural norms, society nature, language diverse and psychological effects. Thus, the need for interpreters to account for differences in participants, cultural backgrounds, norms of discourse and communication protocols, as well as language base (Cornes & Napier, 2005, p. 404).

6.2.1. Linguistically Barriers and Challenges

Interpreters as other language specialists face challenges and difficulties in their duties, in particular interpreters in conflict zones: Each field of translation requires a good knowledge of all underlying vocabulary and terminologies, in addition to its abbreviation and acronyms, otherwise the female translator/interpreter may fail to convey the accurate message. For example, in war context, she must differentiate between different types of attacks: shelling, explosion, airstrike, etc. Similarly, for detention, arrest, enforced disappearance, and captive as each word is used in a special occasion. Barriers such as lack of suitable medical, legal, and scientific terms, lost translation, various dialects, absence of equivalence, various terms. M. Aburisha, (personal communication, November 2, 2020) indicated that lack of equivalence on the lexical level. My work requires me to interpret for workshops that train local professionals on new trends in their fields. All knowledge and concepts are new, and it is very common in conferences and workshops to see a hubbub among the participants regarding how a concept can be expressed in Arabic. This problem appears mainly in humanitarian and developmental workshops. Other issues such as syntax are less important. Somehow it is important to know the pragmatics of speech. Furthermore, updating knowledge with new terms is most challenge that should care about .

6.2.2. Cultural barriers and challenges:

Not understanding various local dialects across Yemen, affecting worker productivity, less asking for more clarifications. Lack of appropriate knowledge about various slangs, Culture, Environment, idioms, jargons, and different cultures. Reference, political opinions, age etc. Culture has affected women's work in the translation field in many aspects like: The deteriorated security situation also represents an additional challenge for female interpreters being part of missions as most of the families will not allow their girl to accept such a work even if they are willing to (G, Bazughifan, personal communication, 1 Novemeber, 2020).

It is hardly a problem. Usually, the participants at conferences use plain language. If the subject is technical, they would use their own jargon. Most cultural issues happen when a speaker makes a joke or cites a proverb. I remember the speaker saying to the participants that she was like a dog, which is acceptable in her context, but I could not translate that. I simply translated the intentional meaning and warned the participants later. In another instance, a speaker used a very vulgar language in Arabic saying that politicians are castrated people. In another case the speaker used very stupid and vulgar sexual language which I interpreted verbatim.

Anyways, those are very rare. Even when they happen, we are not responsible for translating them (M. Aburisha, personal communication, November 2, 2020).

6.2.3. Social barriers and challenges:

Challenges faced by interpreters, particularly female interpreters less they succeed to overcome them, such as working till late hours, in tribal contexts...etc. Also, Religion norms. Religious differences, body language; Being knowledgeable about the social norms of different societies. For instance, female translator/interpreter family may prevent her from going to field visits, as her work is perceived dangers and require a male translator. Movements of female translators in outside resident cities are restricted, requiring authority clearance or being accompanied by a male member of her family as a guardian. For female translators/interpreters that have in mind clear visions, I am sure that they have the ability to work in jeopardy. Women are vulnerable, they may not work in places that require strength, they cannot be fast during attacks/explosions, and it is hard to be in places that are contaminated with landmines (T. Omar, personal communication, February 24, 2020).

6.2.4. Psychological barriers and challenges

Nothing can be a barrier as the fear of no fear. Interpreters may get scared prior attending any meeting, especially if he/ she is not given clear background about the meeting topic. It is the fear of no fear as he/ she is equipped with all needed knowledge and has the ability to convey the clear messages yet fear to fail. Depression and fear in conflict areas most prominent, age differences and tension effect. In order to interpret one have to feel the same feeling of the speaker. This drains the emotional stock and has caused the interpreter distress even made some interpreters cry in the booth many times. They interpret narratives of horrible events. This in addition to other factors has caused them panic attacks and anxiety disorder. They are suffering from that. In addition to other cognitive issues in interpreting. Therefore, may here differentiate between male and female works, for example, a female interpreter in conflict zones, did have the same ability as male interpreters to work in remote distant areas. That will depend on the expected risk level. Gender equality does not mean to have the same ability as men do, it is by understanding the physiological nature of each person, giving him/her tasks that suit this nature. Just because there is a full understanding of his/her interpretative vulnerable, physiological nature. There are social norms that we must understand and follow accordingly. It depends on the circumstances surrounding this conflict zone, he/ she may interpret in IDPs camps, near conflict zones or at hospitals, where many victims were injured due to fighting.

7. Previous Studies

Thajeel (2020) this paper aimed to identified the perspective the media and newspaper about the role of interpreters during American invasion to Iraq. It used a questionnaire that included 30 interpreters who are working in favor of the coalition forces in 2003 in Iraq. The paper also discussed multi roles played by interpreters. The findings of data analysis showed the importance of the roles of the interpreters are devoted to coordination, cultural facilitating and advocacy in addition to being linguists as well. The data also showed that interpreter plays critical roles in conflict zones in mediation and facilitating.

In this regard, Ruiz Rosendo, (2020) probes the role of the emotional in interpreting insoluble conflicts. This paper, based on a joint research project, looked at the experiences of local interpreters and Spanish military personnel who worked in Afghanistan. This paper reached out that emotions shape the interpreter's behavior and have an impact on the interpreter's positionality. This paper has reached the point that emotions shape the behavior of the interpreter and have an impact on the positionality of the interpreter.

In another side, Probirskaja, (2016) probes the narration stories, or plots, that depict Soviet/Russian war/military interpreters. All information gathered from well-known sciences articles, websites and online media articles. This paper follows the military interpreters' stories and news in national great war 1941 -1945 who are participated in the Soviet Union in the 1970s and 1980s, particularly in the war in Afghanistan. The data analysis revealed that storylines described the interpreters as a quiet hero of war.

While Li et al., (2016) dealt with the ethics of interpreters in the resistance war against Japanese aggression in China (1937-1945). The paper emphasized the morality and ethics of the interpreter during the time of war, also other issues such as identity and political aspects. And who interpreter should keep impartiality. The paper's data shows that the interpreter takes away the identity of work and maintains impartiality. Apart from their national identity, the data show that their moral attitude has changed.

Given to multi culturalism aspects, Ruiz Rosendo & Persaud, (2016) examined the role of interpreters in conflict zones in different periods, it discusses the conflict, culture, languages that seems to be common in history of human being, the interpreter's role as culture mediators. This paper aims to take light on the personality, thoughts, impartiality, profession, the role that interpreters play in many stages. the paper reaches out that profession of interpreting work still unsystematic

profession where most of interpreter's lack of adequate training. Also, the community sight underestimates the role of interpreters. There is a massive need to conduct many research and studies that adopted authentic historical view towards the role of interpreters in the time of war.

Based on previous studies mentioned above, noting that most of studies emphasize on one side or two and addressed some issue in foreign or Arabic countries, but in this study the researcher fills the gap of scarce studies in conflict zones in Yemen in addition to discuss four key aspects "language, culture, social and psychological" based on actual study examine the real situation of interpreters in Yemen. This study is a part of huge research work that will be included more aspects and details.

8. Methodology

This study follows qualitative method through using an open-ended questionnaire to achieve the aim of this paper. The researcher found that using online questionnaire is meet the purpose of academic research and suitable for the objective of this study

8.1. Instruments of the study

An online questionnaire has been conducted during 2020/2021. A number of professional interpreters asked voluntarily to take part in an open questionnaire. Using an open questionnaire represent an effective tool to gather a large scale of information about the difficulties and barriers experienced by interpreters. The questionnaire was developed to identify the challenges and barriers that interpreters may encounter in war zone.

8.2. Participants

A number of 10 participants were selected purposively based on the best knowledge of researcher to serve the research purpose and meet question and objective of the study.

9. Discussion, interpretation, and Results:

To answer the question of this study; What are the barriers and challenges that encounter interpreters who are working in conflict zones in Yemen? The researcher developed and conducted an online questionnaire as follows.

- 1- *Have you ever encountered serious situations while interpreting? If yes? Tell us something about your experience.*
- 2- *If you have faced any other challenges, could you please state them here and explain in short?*

The participants were asked to answer these questions based on their previous experience in interpreting in conflict zones. Following the completion of the questionnaire, the analysis process continued as described below. The researcher has coded and sorted data in sort of themes as follows:

Theme one: Language barriers

Language and translation are related to the extent possible as a key factor in the development of civilization. As far as interpreting is concerned, language is the cornerstone of the communication process: knowledge, standards, diversity, system, structure, concepts, etc.... Each field of translation require a good knowledge of all underlying vocabulary and terminologies, in addition to its abbreviation and acronyms, otherwise the female translator/interpreter may fail to convey the accurate message. For example, in war context, she must differentiate between different types of attacks: shelling, explosion, airstrike, etc. Similarly, for detention, arrest, enforced disappearance, and captive as each word is used in a special occasion.

The main challenges that interpreters encounter in conflict zones or armed areas is language barrier that refer to variety of cultures and dialects. Some of the respondents confirmed that language stand behind some barriers that interpreters struggle for. This is noticed by online questionnaire that found different responses. One respondent stated:

"Lack of equivalence on the lexical level. My work requires me to interpret for workshops that train local professionals on new trends in their fields. All knowledge and concepts are new, and it is very common in conferences and workshops to see a hubbub among the participants regarding how a concept can be expressed in Arabic."

Furthermore, language of communications and understanding beyond the meaning, pragmatics; particularly in deliberations, consultations, meetings, seminars, and workshops represented core problem for any interpreter, it is required high qualified knowledge with source and target languages. Thousands of university graduates have no jobs in addition to the lack adequate labor market to absorb them.

One respondent state

"This problem appears mainly in humanitarian, political and developmental consultations, meetings and workshops. Other issues such as syntax are less important. Somehow it is important to know the pragmatics of speech"

During interpreter's work may supposed to take part in multiple tasks such as scientific, political, health, humanitarian, medical and legal contexts.

Another one stated

" Barriers such as lack of suitable medical, political, legal, and scientific terms. "

Another one reported that

" Long sentences, strange words, fixed expressions, long speech and the speaker talking so fast without pausing causes lost in translation, the interpreter is not able to follow up on the conversation on a regular basis "

Some respondents made a link between linguistics barrier and lack experience and practice of the interpreter. They stated that language and interpreter experience are the pushing motives for deliver interpretation precisely and accuracy.

One of the stated

" I think that experience and background of interpreter may play the essential role in understanding the pattern of speech and follow the speaker' speech"

Another one said

"Regarding language, training and practice will enable him to act professionally, I think using professional interpreters could be the best to avoid any linguistics problems and he has a deep experience to handle the situation"

This finding is in line with (Granhagen Jungner et al., 2019) stated that using professional interpreters greatly increased care relationships, patient safety and patient involvement in care and overcome the barrier of language and mistranslation.

Theme Two: Culture barriers:

Therefore, not understanding various local dialects across Yemen, affecting work productivity unless asked for more clarifications

Some respondents stated that culture represent another issue that meet interpreters misunderstanding of culture norms, sensitivity of culture may lead to

critical problem. Therefore, sensitivity of culture should be in considerations. One respondent stated:

" It is hardly a problem. Usually the participants at conferences use plain language. If the subject is technical, they would use their own jargon "

Interpreters may encounter such situations where the speaker said a joke or proverb that consider untranslatability in our language.

Another one stated:

" Most cultural issues happen when a speaker makes a joke or cites a proverb. I remember the speaker saying to the participants that she was like a dog, which is acceptable in her context but I could not translate that. I simply translated the intentional meaning and warned the participants later on. In another instance, a speaker used a very vulgar language in Arabic saying that politicians are castrated people.."

Also, using taboo words or sexual phrases that could be normal in foreign culture and unacceptable in our culture. One respondent stated

" In another case the speaker used very stupid and vulgar sexual language which I interpreted verbatim. Anyways, those are very rare. Even when they happen, we are not responsible for translating them "

Another respondent stated

" Lack of appropriate knowledge about various slangs, idioms, jargons and different cultures. "

These barriers are supported by a news article in SeattleTimes published originally published May 5, 2010, and written by Doug Moore, "The increased number of languages and cultures keeps health care providers constantly on their toes, Bogomolov said". "It's a constant challenge," she said. "But just because a language is exotic, I don't get a pass." (Moore, 2010)

Theme Three: Social barriers:

The respondents reported that one of the difficulties is community sight or society norms, particular against women work as interpreters. Female respondents

said that family may prevent them from going to field visits, as their work is perceived dangerous and require a male translator.

Female interpreter stated

" Challenges faced by female interpreters unless they succeed to overcome them, such as working till late hours, in tribal contexts...etc.
"

Another respondent said

" Being knowledgeable about social norms of different societies"

Another female interpreter said

"Movements of female translators to outside resident city are restricted, requiring authority clearance or being accompanied by a male member from her family as a guardian. "

another one said

"The lack of security in my country push families to prevent their daughter in working in conflict areas"

Social barriers were related to getting married and having a stable family. In addition, the social stress on women was reported to a reason for not hiring women to work in conflict zones in interpreting field by international organizations.

Theme Four: psychological barriers

Nothing can be a barrier as the fear of no fear. Female interpreters may get scared prior attending any meeting, especially if she is not given clear background about the meeting topic. It is the fear of no fear as she is equipped with all needed knowledge and has the ability to convey the clear messages yet fear to fail

There are psychological barriers stated by the respondents. Psychological barriers were based on the fact that interpreters could expose horrible situation and finding their selves under the pressure in their societies. As reported by one of the respondents:

"You cannot generalise. I am talking about myself. In order for me to interpret I have to feel the same feeling of the speaker. This drains my emotional stock and

has caused me distress even made me cry in the booth three times. We interpret narratives of horrible events”.

Another respondent said

Depression and fear in conflict areas. This in addition to other factors has caused me panic attacks and anxiety disorder. I am still suffering from that.

In contrast some respondents stated they have capacity to deal with language and culture barriers but they usual pass by psychological barriers all situation that came as a result to the workload and pressure.

Finally, both male interpreters and female interpreters encounter the same issues in terms of language, culture, social and psychological aspects, and to overcome those barriers needs for educational and professional development, having a qualified education, looking for knowledge and update news and information and other advanced skills.

10. Findings

The findings of the study show that interpreters face many challenges, including linguistic, social, cultural, and psychological challenges, in addition to other external and internal factors such as pressure work, translation lost, workload, security threatening, diversity of dialects, diversity of society, scare, and term conflicts. The findings also show that most interpreters are affected by cultural and psychological factors more than linguistical and social ones.

It is found that psychological, cultural, linguistic, and social factors have a highly imposing effect on the work of interpreters in the conflict areas. Therefore, interpreting is not an easy task, it involves challenges and difficulties related to multi speakers, culture - related references, social factors. During interpreting most interpreters could expect everything and anything in terms of difficulties and barriers that may exist in conflict zones. For example, the nature of interpreting work in conflict, before or post-conflict, and natural disaster situations may impose a such kind of difficulties.

Actually, there are many other external and internal difficulties that this study does not go through it, these difficulties shall consider invisible to document because of confidentiality requirements and the sensitive nature of their work (Tipton 2011; Stahuljak 1999). According to Bello (2014) the profile of war interpreters was quite diverse. Interpreters have been normally locals, that is to say, that they are civilians normally without adequate qualification that simply speak the necessary pair of languages to facilitate communication between soldiers and the population. (p. 66). Most interpreters can be vulnerable while performing normal tasks. Also, Baker (2010) stated that in spite of the potential of the threat. Their work has been always gone beyond what we understand by interpreting. To sum up, this study focus on four challenges and difficulties that were arisen by respondent and found it there are other difficulties may need more study and examine, so to keep consistency in this study, the researcher stick for the above four themes.

11. Conclusion

Translation under umbrella of crises remains the talk show as long as the armed conflict continues in the world. Thus, the open survey revealed and indicated to the barriers and challenges facing interpreters in the field and how language, culture, society, and psychological aspects may play critical roles in the success or failure of an interpreter in the field. To overcome such challenges, the interpreter must have a good preparation and continuous learning. The role played by the interpreter is no less important than the role of negotiators and mediators in wars. It is the link and coordination between the parties. Without the interpreter, dialogue or negotiations cannot take place. Finally, the interpreter looks forward to finding appreciation and gratitude from the community for his roles in facilitating and enhancing the role of workers in international organizations and regional mediators.

12. Recommendations

Upon the data findings the study has some recommendations; interpreters should have a strong experience and background about the field of translation. Interpreters should have negotiation skills and the ability to work under pressure and hostile areas. Interpreters should keep impartiality and confidentiality and receive adequate training about working in conflict zones. More further studies in Yemeni context are advisable. The study also recommended the interpreters to be aware of cultural sensitivity and to avoid psychological pressure and tension. This study context discussion was restricted to four dimensions, there are other dimensions this study did not go beyond and let the door open to further studies and research in this regard.

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